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DIACHRONIC STUDY OF TAXIS

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Аннотация: Мақолада таксис категорияси тадқиқ этилишининг тарихий тадрижи ҳақида сўз боради. Асосан, рус ва герман тилшунослигида мазкур категориянинг ўрганилиши қиёсий аспектда таҳлил этилган. Шунингдек, кенг тарқалган турли концепциялар асносида таксис умумий назариясига даҳлдор турфа хил нуқтайи назарлар келтирилади.

Калит сўзлар: таксис, категория, концепция, муносабат, функционал-семантик, морфологик, мазмун-план, ифода-план.

Аннотация: В статье, преимущественно в русском и германском языкознании, сравнительно проанализирована эволюция исследования категории таксиса в диахроническом аспекте. Также, излагаются разные точки зрения по категории таксиса в свете существующих распространенных концепций.

Ключевые слова: таксис, категория, концепция, отношение, функционально-семантический, морфологический, план-содержания, план-выражения.

Abstract: Diachronic research evolution of taxis, mainly in Russian and German linguistics, has been comparatively analyzed in the paper. Various standpoints on taxis category in light of various prevalent conceptions are expatiated on, as well.

Keywords: taxis, category, conception, relation, functional-semantic, morphological, content-plan, expression-plan.

INTRODUCTION

In linguistic literature, the term “taxis” was initially used by R.O. Jakobson in his published work “Shifters, Verbal Categories and the Russian Verb” (1957). However, the emergence of scientific interest for this category and its detailed elaboration began only after the translation of this article into Russian, published in a research paper entitled “The Principles of Typological Analysis of Different Systems Languages” (1972).

In general linguistics, this category has traditionally been considered within two standpoints, i.e. from syntactical standpoint related to the problem of the structural specificity of the complex sentence and from aspectological standpoint related to the functions of grammatical category of aspect. However, both aspects of the study of the issue have not been sufficiently generalized.

So far, the category of taxis has been studied mainly in the context of syntactic studies. This is due to the fact that the main “burden” in the actualizaion of taxis relations in the Russian and Roman-Germanic languages rests on syntax level (paradigm). The regularities of taxis relations are most often caused by the structural frame of the constructions in which verb forms are involved [Hanbalaeva, 2011].

There is also a case in which Jakobson's theory can be used to justify the category of taxis as being more syntactical than grammatical. For example, according to R.O. Jakobson, “The category of tense itself acts as taxis in a subordinate taxis; it (i.e. the tense) refers to time (tense) relations of the major reported incident; not to the act of speech, as in an independent taxis” [Jakobson, 1972].

In Russian linguistics, the category of taxis for the first time was depicted in a series of monographic works by A.Vostokov’s in “Russian Grammar (1831); A.M. Peshkowskiy’s “Russian Syntax in Scientific Interpretation” (1914); A.A. Shakhmatov's "Syntax of the Russian Language" (1941); I.A. Popova's "Compound Sentence in the Modern Russian Language" (1950); it has also been published in a series of monographs by N.S. Pospelov in his monograph "On the Grammatical Nature and Principles of the Classification of Asyndetic Composite Sentences" (1950).

Further, taxis has also been extensively studied on the example of Russian subordinate clauses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study of taxis relations in Russian linguistics can be conditionally divided into two: 1). the stage studied as a secondary semantic meaning, and, 2). the stage studied directly under the term taxis itself [Azisova, 2004: 36].

The current development of the issue provides a good basis for the taxis relationships to be separated into a separate analysis. Nevertheless, it is possible to say that the category of taxis is not recognized unanimously in modern linguistics. The interactions of actions (facts) in the modern world are interpreted by many linguists as elements of other semantic, namely temporality and aspect, as well as transient, temporal and aspect-taxis categories. The reason for such conflicts is not only in the complexity of the object being described, but also in the importance of the interpretation of the terms "aspect", "temporality" and "taxis" in the works of various authors. The complexity and diversity of taxis semantics, its role in the system of different grammatical categories, the structure of taxis-pairs and the content description of taxis can even be found among linguists who consider taxis as an independent category.

Today, there are two main concepts that differ principally from the existing taxis concepts that recognize it as an independent category:

The priority relationship between action(fact)s as the main component of the taxis content-plan, and the morphological concept of "perfect / non-perfect" as a key component of the expression-plan. However, it is not difficult to notice that taxis is included in this interpretation as another distinct term for the grammatical category of tense relativity (reference or phase) [Lyashchenko, 2007; Azisova 2004; Nematullaeva, 2002].

As a key component of the taxis-plan, all three types of chronological relationships (priority, simultaneity, and posteriority), and as a key component of the expression- plan, combine different levels (lexical, grammatical, lexical- grammatical

and syntactic). A functional-semantic concept consisting of a large inventory of different polypredicative structures with a specific relationship. This approach is the basis of our research.

We, like many researchers [see: Mishaeva, 2007; Maksimova, 2005; Panin, 1992; Semyonova, 2004; Sydneyhe, 1991; Malikov, 2005; Toechkina, 2004; Khanbalaeva, 2005, 2011; Lyashchenko, 2007; Azisova, 2004; Nematullaeva, 2002, and others] regard taxis as a functional-semantic category (FSC), which includes various means of chronological relationships between two or more event(fact)s during a single time-plan. The functional- semantic taxis category deals with the Logical Category of Taxis (Order) (LCT) [Bondarko, 1983].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The group of linguists led by A.V. Bondarko, during the 1980s and 1990s, carried out a major project called "Theory of Functional Grammar". In the series of monographs, created in 1987-1996, such Functional-Semantic Fields as Aspectuality, Time Localization (in Russian: временная локализованность), Taxis (in Russian: таксис), Temporality, Modality, Personality, Voiceness, Subjectivity, Objectivity, Communicative Perspective, Definetness, Locality, Existence, Possessiveness, Conditionality were elucidated. The main task in describing each field was to take the inventory of the meanings and the formal expression means that are relevant to the actual field. A.V. Bondarko's approaches, mainly based on Russian language material, also include partial comparisons [Bondarko, 1983; 1984; 1987 et al.]. A number of issues were also expatiated on by V.S. Khrakowski, V.P. Nedyalkov, A.P. Volodin. The category has also been studied by N.A. Kozintseva and other linguists on the material of different languages or within typological aspects [see: Khrakovsky, 1987, 2001; Nedyalkov, 1990, 2001; Kozintseva, 1987, 1991, etc.].

Prominent Petersburg taxis researchers, such as A.V. Bondarko, T.G. Akimova, N.A. Kozintseva consider it as a functional- semantic category based on the interrelation (and interconnection) of semantic elements of various language layers (and paradigms), such as morphological (aspectual oppositions), lexical-grammatical

(some conjunctions, prepositions, adverbs), and syntactic (certain types of poly-predicative sentences) [TFG, 1987].

M.Y. Ryabova who studied taxis relations in the English language material had striven to encompass at most not only morphological and lexical characteristics, but also other, above all, syntactic aspects of expression-plan of this category. In her research, she additionally covered various types of presuppositions and implications. In the category of taxis relations, the author includes virtually all types of poly-predicative expressions that are below the level of mono-predicative expressions of both synthetic and complex syntactic integrity and various semantic complexities [see: Ryabova, 1995]. Likewise, taxis was interpreted in the materials of the French and Russian languages by N.V. Bernitskaya [see: Bernitskaya, 1999: 17].

O. Akhmanova, S. Belenkaya (with reference to English) and A.I. Borodina (with reference to English and German) are known to strictly associate taxis with the "perfect : non-perfekt" opposition, which represents the "priority" relations and is known as "relative time" in traditional germanism and anglism. In doing so, they assigned taxis mainly to the morphological category. The terms of this opposition and the semantic-syntactic and lexical-semantic aspects of this opposition are usually not included or described in their research [see: Borodina, 1975; et al.].

According to A.I. Smirnitkiy, the English taxis category does not correspond to the category of time reference (in Russian: категорияотнесенности) by its semantic scope [Smirnitkiy, 1983]. Because, taxis, besides morphological forms also actively involve syntactic structures of various formats and complexities.

L. Blumfield, B. Lee Warf and R.O. Jakobson were one of the first pioneers of taxis phenomenon who developed and analyzed it in the language material, where taxis relations (semantics) are represented by a system of special morphological units. The further development of taxis theory is mainly based on the example of Russian, German and Romanian material, which is represented in the field of taxonomic constructive syntax [see: Arhipova, 1998; Barieva, 2005; Bezrodnova, 2009; Bernitskaya, 1999; Borodina, 1975; Vyalsova, 2008; Gareeva, 2003, et al]. Thus, to date taxis has been

studied mainly within the functional-semantic approach. At the same time, the phormo-centric approach commonly used to describe it has shifted to a second plan. The study of taxis in the languages where it's expressed morphologically, that is, as an independent category of the verb, is not yet sufficiently developed. It can be stated that acquaintance with the language materials where taxis is an independent verbal category (expressed morphologically) provided the necessary basis for the analysis and development of taxis category in general [Khanbalaeva, 2011].

Taxis relations represented by a special paradigm of the verbal morphological categories include such languages as Dagestania (Lezghin, Dargwa, and Avarian), whereas there is no morphological taxis category, and this gap is mainly compensated by syntactical means are Russian, English and other similar languages.

Modern taxis theory relies mainly on language materials that do not have a morphological taxis category. Conversely, such languages with morphological taxis category as Dagestania and Turkic have always been neglected in the formulation of general theories about taxis [see: Khanbalaeva, 2011: 29].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, so far no special research has been devoted to the problem of taxis in general and to the semantic relationship among its grammatical means of representation in the Turkic languages, especially in Uzbek linguistics. Nevertheless, it is important to note that the language phenomena related to the category of taxis have, to some extent, been partly studied, even if under different terminology, in published research and general work on Turkic, particularly Uzbek, Tatar and Tuva languages [see: Sayfullaeva, 2010; Salchak, 2006; Azisova, 2004, et al].

In this context, a comprehensive study of taxis in Turkish linguistics, namely in Uzbek, is one of the most pressing issues, especially in the comparative-typological framework where it should be compared with the Slavic (particularly, Russian) and Roman-German (particularly, French, German, and English) languages in which taxis is studied relatively in detail.

REFERENCES

Jacobson R.O. Shifters, Verbal Categories and the Russian Verb. Translated from English in the book: Principles of a Typological Analysis of Languages of Different Systems. - M., 1972.

Khanbalaeva S.N. Allomorphy of the expression of taxis relations (based on the Russian, Lezgin, Dargin, Avarian and English Languages): Abstract. diss. doc. filol. sciences. - Moscow, 2011. - 52 p.

Azisova M.S. Taxis in the modern Tatar literary language: Diss. cand. filol. sciences. - Kazan, 2004. - 175 p.

Nematullaeva M.N. Typology of the expression of taxis relations (based on Tajik and English): Author. diss. cand. filol. sciences. - Khujand, 2002.

Maksimova L.Y. Undifferentiated taxis relations: on the material of English and Russian: Abstract. disc. cand. filol. sciences. - Kemerovo, 2005.

Panin E.I. Verbs with taxis seme in modern German: Abstract. diss. cand. filol. sciences. - M., 1992.

Semenova N.V. Taxis category in modern Russian (02/10/01): Abstract. diss. doc. filol. sciences. - Veliky Novgorod, 2004.

Sidinha A.L. The semantics of the verbs of physical perception and the taxis-aspectual component of the sentences they organize in modern English: Abstract. diss. cand. filol. sciences. - Odessa, 1991.

Malikov A.V. Explanatory constructions: semantics of the reference word and taxis: Abstract. diss. cand. filol. sciences.
- Moscow, 2005.

Toechkina O.A. The implementation of the taxis value of simultaneity in modern English (based on the material of economic discourse): Diss. cand. filol. sciences. - St. Petersburg, 2004. - 175 p.

Bondarko A.V. Theory of morphological categories. - L., 1976. - 254 p.

Nedyalkov V.P. The main types of participles // Typology and Grammar: Sat. Art. - M.: Nauka, 1990. - P. 36-59.

Исаров О. Таксис категориал ҳолатлари ва таксис ифодаловчи феъл комбинациялари // Вестник Каракалпакского государственного университета имени Бердаха. – 2011. – Т. 13. – №. 3-4. – С. 117-118.

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